

Enabling Force Controllability by Mechanics in Exoskeleton Design

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Abstract—This paper uses a simple interaction model to motivate existing issues in exoskeleton force control and proposes a solution to tackle these issues by mechanical design.

I. INTRODUCTION

Force control is one of the most critical feature in nowadays exoskeletons. In spite of the amount of existing literature and solutions, in most of the cases accurate force control is still a challenging problem. Main challenges in exoskeleton force control include dealing with the uncertain human dynamics [1] and sizing actuators to obtain both high torque capabilities and low reflected inertia, which are usually contrasting requirements.

The main objective of this paper is to highlight a novel perspective in exoskeleton design which explicitly considers force controllability as a primal requirement for mechanical design. In the proposed approach force control issues are tackled in two steps. In the first step, mechanical design aims at building inherently torque controllable systems by following the guidelines described hereafter. In particular, we motivate how some mechanical choices can lower the sensitivity to environment uncertainties thus leading to improve force controllability. In the second step, control design is asked to guarantee the desired performance and dealing with remain uncertainties.

II. MODELING

The rationale to motivate our approach is based on the simple interaction models in Figure 1 where angular variables (angles and torques) are translated into linear equivalents (linear positions and forces). These models represent an actuator, characterized by a motor inertia J_m and a series stiffness k , connected to a robot link or exoskeleton frame with inertia J . The link is in contact with a *downstream dynamics* represented in terms of external forces τ_{ext} (Figure 1a). The downstream dynamics can represent the human the robot is in contact with, eventually including the dynamics of distal joints and human-robot physical interfaces. The model in Figure 1a can be written as

$$J_m \ddot{\theta} = \tau_m - \tau_s \quad (1)$$

$$\tau_s = k(\theta - q) \quad (2)$$

$$J \ddot{q} = \tau_s - \tau_{ext} \quad (3)$$

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and is used here to highlight the importance of the parameter

$$\rho = \frac{J_m}{J} \quad (4)$$

which characterizes the sensitivity to downstream uncertainties, e.g. given by the uncertain human dynamics. Indeed, it is possible to arrange the model (1)-(3) as

$$\frac{J_m}{k} \ddot{\tau}_s + (1 + \rho)\tau_s = \tau_m + \rho\tau_{ext} \quad (5)$$

where it is evident that the parameter ρ modulates the effect of the external torque τ_{ext} . Indeed, when ρ tends to zero the force dynamics is no longer influenced by the external torque τ_{ext} from the downstream dynamics. Conversely, for high values of ρ the force dynamics is highly influenced by the external torque τ_{ext} . The definition of the sensitivity parameter ρ in (4) can suggest two approaches to reduce the sensitivity to the human uncertainties by mechanics: lowering the motor inertia J_m and/or augmenting the exoskeleton inertia J . While the first approach is rather intuitive and supported by authors previous results [2], the second is more controversial. Indeed, an increased frame inertia can hinder the transparent interaction with the user. Being the frame distal with respect to the force sensor, force feedback cannot mask its inertia thus preventing a high-transparency interaction, especially in the case of high frame inertia J . This is because the actuator forces are usually measured by deflection of the series elastic element which, apart from static conditions, cannot measure the interaction forces with the wearer, especially for high J . As a possible solution one can think to arrange a force sensor directly on the wearer ergonomic interface, however, even in this case performance limitations occur because of non collocation of sensor and actuator [3]. In conclusion, deliberately introducing additional inertia on the exoskeleton frames is often not a desirable solution. The approach of reducing the motor inertia J_m is certainly preferable and is the one considered in this paper. Reducing the motor inertia is not a trivial task because it affect the motor torque capabilities. For examples, high torques can be obtained by augmenting the transmission ratio k_r , which increases the rotor inertia by a factor k_r^2 and/or by increasing the number of magnetic or electric poles, which implies more magnets or wires. Thus, in this study we put our focus not only on the selection of motor with high torque-inertia ratio but primarily on reducing the actuator torque requirements by proper mechanical design, as described in the next section.

Figure 1. The considered interaction models.

III. EXOSKELETON DESIGN

The proposed exoskeleton design is represented in Figure 2. In its preliminary version it is characterized by a planar structure which includes two degrees of freedom: one at the shoulder and one at the elbow. To reduce the actuator torque requirements the first link is designed using a parallelogram structure allowing accurate gravity compensation on the whole arm and to avoid torque propagation between consecutive joints. The latter feature is given by the parallelogram kinematic constraints which do not allow rotation of the triangular plate between the two links. The same constraint is exploited for gravity compensation on the elbow joint: differently from traditional serial kinematics, the orientation of the forearm link does not depend on the shoulder joint, allowing to implement gravity compensation using a tendon driven elastic element with simple routing, as represented in Figure 3.

To ensure good force controllability we consider the parameter ρ and the interaction model in Figure 1b which can be formulated by replacing (3) with

$$J\ddot{q} + d\dot{q} + hq = \tau_s \quad (6)$$

where d and h represent the dominant damping and stiffness parameters of the downstream dynamics. Again, the following equation motivates that the parameter ρ modulates the effect of stiffness (hq) and damping ($d\dot{q}$) forces

$$\frac{J_m}{k}\ddot{\tau}_s + (1 + \rho)\tau_s = \tau_m + \rho(hq + d\dot{q}). \quad (7)$$

This model is then used in simulation to analyze the exoskeleton controllability for different values of inertia J , stiffness h and damping d parameters plausible for the specific application. In particular, the considered values of J are sampled from all the possible kinematic configurations of the exoskeleton and the same for the parameter h which accounts for the (linearized) residual gravity forces. Results from iterative simulation trials indicate that, for the elbow joint, a rotor inertia $J_m < 0.013 \text{ kgm}^2$ allows adequate robustness to downstream dynamics uncertainties while a rotor inertia less than $J_m < 0.06 \text{ kgm}^2$ guarantees the same propriety

Figure 2. The proposed exoskeleton design concept. The parallelogram structure avoids torque propagation and passive gravity compensation.

Figure 3. Representation of the passive gravity compensation mechanism implemented using one spring at the elbow joint and one at the shoulder joint.

for the shoulder joint. Considering the specific joint torque requirements (not reported) we considered a Maxon DCX22L motor with reduction ratio 103:1 leading to a reflected inertia of $J_m < 0.012 \text{ kgm}^2$.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Basing on the fact that mechanical design can significantly influence force controllability, this paper briefly introduces an exoskeleton design approach which guarantees low sensitivity to wearer dynamics and uncertainties by mechanical design. The method is motivated by a theoretical insight which defines a sensitivity parameter as the ration of motor and frame inertia. Then appropriate motor inertias are found by iterative simulation trials. The prototype will be presented at the I-RIM 3D event where experimental characterizations of force control performance and robustness will be reported.

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